

Development of Reliability Model for Evaluating the Level of Performance of Used Motor Vehicle Engine

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Abstract

The most popular means of transportation is the road transport for the movement of goods and services. The reliability performance of engines of used vehicles has become a major concern for a number of reasons ranging from pollution and degradation of environment to high cost of repairs and maintenance. Up till present time, there is no mean of ascertaining the reliability of used vehicles in Nigeria. In order to prevent this country from being turned to a dumping ground for obsolete and not useful vehicle, there is a need for reliability evaluating tool to ascertain the level of reliability of the used vehicle. Therefore, the work aim at development of a model for determining the reliability of engines of used vehicles being imported into the country. The research presented the analysis of each components of automobile engine used to validate the model based on the result of model developed. The model developed is called Reliability and Maintenance Model (RMM) which is capable of computing the reliability of many mechanical systems in the engine. The result of the reliability model validation of Nissan Primera 1990 model used is 1.1209×10^{-4} .

Keywords: Reliability, Performance, Evaluation, Used Vehicle Engines.

Introduction

The economic history of Nigeria is largely the story of the opening of its vast areas by various forms of transport and transport problems of a city are related to its size and shape, (Omionu and Onokerhoraye, 1995). In Nigeria today, the most popular means of transportation is the road transport, as other options such as rail, sea or air are either not functional or within the economic reach of the majority of the population. The role of transport in economic progress is further highlighted by Teravaninthorn and Rabelland, (2006) who observed that the cost of transporting goods in Africa, being the highest in the world, was one of the reasons for the slow economic growth being witnessed in the continent. Cities are creatures of transportation and were not possible until transportation allowed the necessary movements of food, raw materials, products and services, (Pederson, 1980).

Schwela and Zali, (1999) recognized motor vehicles as the major contributor to urban air pollution. The products of combustion from

internal combustion engines contain several constituents that are considered hazardous to human health, including Carbon monoxide(CO), Unburnt hydrocarbons(UHCs), Nitrogen Oxide (NO₂) (Oke *et al*, 2011).

However, due to changing economic situation and the impact of Structural Adjustment Policy (SAP), the supply of new vehicles of all types began to decrease in 1982, while the importation of used vehicles gained momentum. In 2004, annual sales of used vehicles in Nigeria was 29,000 units, with a further 25% or so being smuggled into the country illegally through the land borders, (AAWA, 2006). It should be pointed out that a few existing assembly facilities have an annual installed capacity of about 100,000 units. However, the low per capita income in Nigeria adversely affects the affordability of new vehicles. Ikya , 1993) carried out a survey which showed that between 1982 and 1989, the number of new vehicle registrations per annum fell from 224,000 to approximately 50,000. The economic situation and lack of protection for automobile assembly plants in

Nigeria have encouraged the importation of used vehicles from abroad, thus, the country has become a dumping ground for all sorts of vehicles from all countries of the globe.

Therefore, since 1998, a number of policies based on age or year of manufacture of vehicle have been formulated by the Federal Government of Nigeria to regulate importation and ensure improved quality of used vehicles imported into the country. The objective of these policies is to ensure that only reliable used vehicles found their ways into the country's transportation system. These policies notwithstanding, problems such as pollution and degradation of environment, loss of man – hour, personal inconveniences to vehicle owners/ users and loss of resources due to frequent breakdown have been identified with used vehicles being imported into the country.

Aside the health consideration, many problems associated with used vehicles being imported into the country has given rise to the need to find means of evaluating the reliability of these vehicles before importation. Reliability

is the probability of performing without failure, specific function under given conditions for a specified period of time and is the probability that unsatisfactory performance or failure will not occur, (Robert, 2015). Reliability improvement is a natural consequence of failure analysis, as the probability of a device performing its purpose adequately for a period of time intended under the operating conditions encountered, (Carab Tekniva Group, 2012).

The reliability performance of engines of these used vehicles has become a major concern for a number of reasons ranging from pollution and degradation of environment to high cost of repairs and maintenance. Therefore, it becomes imperative to develop a tool to predict the performance reliability of the engines of used vehicles before being allowed into the country. In developing the reliability model for evaluating the motor vehicle engine, there is a need to carry out physical system analysis that will translate system to reliability network (Billinton and Allan, 1985).

Materials and Methods

The methods used to achieve the set objectives of this research work include the following:

Selection of a four-stroke cycle Engine:-
 Identification of components parts of engine of a motor vehicle;
 Identification of the component parts that directly affect the

reliability of performance of the engine;
 Arrangement of the component parts into major and minor segments;
 Development and evaluation of the model base on the arrangements.

Fig. 1: Automobile Engine Oil System, (AA1 Car.com, 2015)

Formulation of mathematical Model

In network modelling of the systems, it involves to translate the analysis of the physical systems into a reliability network using the operational logic with the basic knowledge of the physical behaviour of the system. The engine components were arranged in series and parallel in this work study.

Fig. 2: Four- stroke cycle Engine (Encarta Encyclopaedia, 2009)

Piston Sub-Assembly, A: A₁ - Engine Block
 A₂ - Cylinder Head, A₃ - Cylinder (Bore),
 A₃₁ - Cylinder Gasket, A₃₂ - Stud, A₄ - Piston
 Ring, A₄₁ - Compression Ring, A₄₂ - Scraper
 Ring, A₅ - Piston.

Fig.3: Piston Sub-Assembly Block diagram

Mathematical model for Piston Sub-Assembly (A) in series/parallel as shown in Fig. 3 and the formulated equation is as given in (4) and (5).

$$R_{PS} = R_{A1} \cdot R_{A2} \cdot [(1 - F_{A31} \cdot F_{A32})] \cdot R_{A3} \cdot [(1 - F_{A41} \cdot F_{A42})] \cdot R_{A4} \cdot R_{A5} \quad (2)$$

$$R_{PS} = (1 - F_{A31} \cdot F_{A32})(1 - F_{A41} \cdot F_{A42}) R_{A1} \cdot R_{A2} \cdot R_{A3} \cdot R_{A4} \cdot R_{A5} \quad (3)$$

R_A = Reliability of the Piston Assembly

$$R_A = [(1 - (1 - R_{A31})(1 - R_{A32}))(1 - (1 - R_{A41})(1 - R_{A42}))] R_{A1} \cdot R_{A2} \cdot R_{A3} \cdot R_{A4} \cdot R_{A5} \quad (4)$$

Mathematical model was formulated to represent the reliability of each of the sub-assemblies identified and for the engine as a unit is as given in (1).

$$R = R_A \cdot R_B \cdot R_C \cdot R_D \cdot R_E \cdot R_F \cdot R_G \quad (1)$$

where

R = Reliability of Engine

Mathematical model for Sub assembly

$$R_A = \left[1 - \prod_{j=1}^2 (1 - R_{A_{3j}}) \right] \left[1 - \prod_{j=1}^2 (1 - R_{A_{4j}}) \right] \left[\prod_{i=1}^5 R_{A_i} \right] \quad (5)$$

Connecting Rod Sub-Assembly, B: B₁ - Connecting rod, B₁₁ - Bushing, B₁₂ - Bearing, B₂ - Gudgeon Pin, B₂₁ - Circlip Ring.

Fig. 4: Connecting Rod Sub-Assembly Block diagram

Mathematical model for Connecting Rod Sub-Assembly (B) in parallel/series as shown in Fig. 4 and the formulated equation is as given in (8) and (9).

$$R_{CR} = (1 - F_{B11} F_{B12}) R_{B1} \cdot R_{B21} \cdot R_{B2} \quad (6)$$

$$R_{CR} = [1 - (1 - R_{B11})(1 - R_{B12})] R_{B1} \cdot R_{B21} \cdot R_{B2} \quad (7)$$

R_B = Reliability of the Connecting Rod Assembly

$$R_B = [1 - (1 - R_{B11})(1 - R_{B12})] R_{B1} \cdot R_{B21} \cdot R_{B2} \quad (8)$$

$$R_B = \left[1 - \prod_{j=1}^2 (1 - R_{B_{ij}}) \right] [R_{B_{21}} \prod_{i=1}^2 R_{B_i}] \quad (9)$$

Crankshaft Sub-Assembly, C: C₁- Crankshaft, C₁₁- Journal bearing, C₁₂ - Thrust washer, C₁₃ - Main bearing, C₂ - Flywheel.

Fig. 5: Crankshaft Sub-Assembly Block diagram

Mathematical Model for Crankshaft Sub-Assembly(C) in parallel/series as shown in Fig. 5 and the formulated equation is as given in (12) and (13).

$$R_{CK} = (1 - F_{C11}F_{C12}F_{C13}) R_{C1} \cdot R_{C2} \quad (10)$$

$$R_{CK} = [1 - [(1 - R_{C11})(1 - R_{C12})(1 - R_{C13})]] R_{C1} \cdot R_{C2} \quad (11)$$

R_C = Reliability of the Crankshaft Sub-Assembly

$$R_C = [1 - [(1 - R_{C11})(1 - R_{C12})(1 - R_{C13})]] R_{C1} \cdot R_{C2} \quad (12)$$

$$R_C = \left[1 - \prod_{j=1}^3 (1 - R_{C_{ij}}) \right] \left[\prod_{i=1}^2 R_{C_i} \right] \quad (13)$$

Camshaft Sub-Assembly, D: D₁- Camshaft, D₁₁- Timing chain, D₁₂ - timing Cover,

D₁₃ - Gasket, D₁₄ - Chain adjuster, D₁₅ - Pump driving pinion, D₂ - Engine Valves, D₃- Cams.

Fig. 6: Camshaft Sub- Assembly Block diagram

Mathematical Model for Camshaft Sub- Assembly (D) in parallel/series as shown in Fig. 6 and the formulated equation is as given in (16) and (17).

$$R_{CM} = (1 - F_{D11}F_{D12}F_{D13}F_{D14}F_{D15}) R_{D1} \cdot R_{D2} \cdot R_{D3} \quad (14)$$

$$R_{CM} = ((1 - (1 - R_{D11})(1 - R_{D12})(1 - R_{D13})(1 - R_{D14})(1 - R_{D15})) R_{D1} \cdot R_{D2} \cdot R_{D3} \quad (15)$$

R_D = Reliability of Camshaft Sub-Assembly

$$R_D = ((1 - (1 - R_{D11})(1 - R_{D12})(1 - R_{D13})(1 - R_{D14})(1 - R_{D15})) R_{D1} \cdot R_{D2} \cdot R_{D3} \quad (16)$$

$$R_D = \left[1 - \prod_{j=1}^5 (1 - R_{D_{ij}}) \right] \left[\prod_{i=1}^3 R_{D_i} \right] \quad (17)$$

[Rocker Sub-Assembly, E]: E₁- Rockers, E₂ - Push Rods, E₃ - Tappets.

Fig. 7: Rocker Sub- Assembly Block diagram

Mathematical Model for Rocker Sub-Assembly (E) in series as shown in Fig. 7 and the formulated equation is as given in (19).

$$R_{RK} = R_{E1} \cdot R_{E2} \cdot R_{E3} \quad (18)$$

R_E = Reliability of the Rocker Sub-Assembly

$$R_E = \prod_{i=1}^3 R_{E_i} \quad (19)$$

[Pumping Sub-Assembly, F]: F₁ - Oil Pump, F₂ - Oil Sump, F₃ - Oil filter.

Fig. 8: Pumping Sub-Assembly Block diagram

Mathematical Model for of the Pumping Sub-Assembly (F) in series as shown in Fig. 8 and the formulated equation is as given in (21) and (22).

$$R_{PP} = R_{F1} \cdot R_{F2} \cdot R_{F3} \quad (20)$$

R_F = Reliability of the Pumping Sub-Assembly

$$R_F = R_{F1}R_{F2}R_{F3} \quad (21)$$

$$R_F = \prod_{i=1}^3 R_{Fi} \quad (22)$$

[Cooling Sub-Assembly, G]: G_1 - Radiator, G_2 - Fan, G_3 - Water Pump

Fig. 9: Cooling System Sub-Assembly Block diagram

Mathematical Model for Cooling System Sub-Assembly (G) in series as shown in Fig. 9 and the formulated equation is as given in (24) and (25)

$$R_{CS} = R_{G1} \cdot R_{G2} \cdot R_{G3} \quad (23)$$

R_G = reliability of the Cooling Sub-Assembly

$$R_G = R_{G1} \cdot R_{G2} \cdot R_{G3} \quad (24)$$

$$R_G = \prod_{i=1}^3 R_{Gi} \quad (25)$$

$$R_R = R_{PS} \cdot R_{CR} \cdot R_{CK} \cdot R_{CM} \cdot R_{RK} \cdot R_{PP} \cdot R_{CS} = [(1 - (1 - R_{A31})(1 - R_{A32})(1 - (1 - R_{A41})(1 - R_{A42})))R_{A1} \cdot R_{A2} \cdot R_{A3} \cdot R_{A4} \cdot R_{A5}] \cdot [(1 - (1 - R_{B11})(1 - R_{B12}))R_{B1} \cdot R_{B21} \cdot R_{B2}] \cdot [(1 - (1 - R_{C11})(1 - R_{C12})(1 - R_{C13}))R_{C1} \cdot R_{C2}] \cdot [((1 - (1 - R_{D11})(1 - R_{D12})(1 - R_{D13})(1 - R_{D14})(1 - R_{D15}))R_{D1} \cdot R_{D2} \cdot R_{D3} \cdot R_{D4}) \cdot [R_{E1} \cdot R_{E2} \cdot R_{E3}] \cdot [R_{F1} \cdot R_{F2} \cdot R_{F3}] \cdot [R_{G1} \cdot R_{G2} \cdot R_{G3}] \quad (26)$$

The reliability of the fairly used engine can be expressed in terms of failure rate is as given in (27).

$$R = \left[1 - \prod_{j=1}^2 (1 - R_{A_{3j}})\right] \left[1 - \prod_{j=1}^2 (1 - R_{A_{ij}})\right] \left[\prod_{i=1}^5 R_{A_i}\right] \left[1 - \prod_{j=1}^2 (1 - R_{B_{ij}})\right] \left[R_{B_{21}} \prod_{i=1}^2 B_i\right] \left[1 - \prod_{j=1}^3 (1 - R_{C_{ij}})\right] \left[\prod_{i=2}^2 R_{C_i}\right] \left[1 - \prod_{j=1}^5 (1 - R_{D_{ij}})\right] \left[\prod_{i=1}^3 R_{D_i}\right] \left[\prod_{i=1}^3 R_{E_i} R_{F_i} R_{G_i}\right] \quad (27)$$

Validation of the Model

The model developed for determining reliability of engines of used vehicles was validated using data obtained from laboratory test and experiments carried out on the major

and minor components that were considered in building the model.

The test carried out was hardness test, a Non Destructive Test (NDT), using the Micro Hardness Testing machine installed in the Material Testing laboratory of the Engineering Materials Development Institute, Akure, Ondo state, Nigeria.

The car model used for the validation was a Nissan Primera 1990 model and procedure adopted in validating the model was as follows:

(i) The automotive parts considered in building the model were sourced for from an automobile workshop.

(ii) The parts were prepared into samples for use on the hardness testing machine.

(iii) Using the GRANTA engineering software, the hardness value for each of the basic material for the automotive parts was established. This value was taken as Standard Value (b).

(iv) Using the Micro Hardness Testing machine, the hardness value for each of the samples was determined. This value was taken as Investigated Value (a).

(v) The ratio of Investigated Value to Standard Value was calculated and taken to be the Reliability for each of the sample i.e. $R = \frac{\alpha}{\beta}$

(vi) Using the established relationship in theory of reliability that is;

$$\text{Probability of Survival} + \text{Probability of Failure} = 1, R + F = 1$$

The probability of failure was determined for each of the samples.

(vii) The values of F obtained in (6) were used as failure probabilities in the reliability model earlier developed in this study.

(viii) The time period considered for the validation of the model was twenty (20) years.

Results

Using the values of reliability obtained from the experimental test as shown in table 1 and substituting these values into the

mathematical equation defining the reliability for each sub-assembly unit, the value of reliability obtained was 1.1209×10^{-4} .

Table 1: Reliability and Failure Rate of the Used Motor Vehicle Engine

S/N	Name of Component	Reliability, R	Failure, F
		$R = \frac{\alpha}{\beta}$	(1-R)
A	Piston Assembly		
1	Engine block	0.80	0.20
2	Cylinder head	0.68	0.32
3	Cylinder gasket	0.68	0.32
4	Stud	0.60	0.40
5	Compression ring	0.87	0.13
6	Oil scrapper ring	0.52	0.48
7	Piston	0.61	0.39
8	Cylinder bore	0.68	0.32
Average		0.68	0.32
B	Connecting Rod Assembly		
1	Bearing (Brass)	0.72	0.28
2	Bushing (metal)	0.72	0.28
3	Connecting rod	0.69	0.31
4	Gudgeon pin	0.68	0.32
5	Circlip ring	0.75	0.25
Average		0.71	0.29
C	Crankshaft Assembly		
1	Crankshaft	0.67	0.33
2	Journal bearing	0.70	0.30
3	Thrust washer	0.81	0.19
4	Main bearing	0.70	0.30
5	Flywheel	0.63	0.37
Average		0.70	0.30
D	Camshaft Assembly		
1	Camshaft	0.78	0.22
2	Timing chain	0.78	0.22
3	Timing cover	0.79	0.21
4	Gasket	0.80	0.20
5	Chain adjuster	0.79	0.21
6	Pump driving pinion	0.58	0.42
7	Engine valves	0.78	0.22
8	Cam	0.61	0.39
Average		0.74	0.26
E	Rocker Assembly		

1	Rocker shaft	0.70	0.30
2	Push rods	0.70	0.30
3	Tappets	0.68	0.32
Average		0.70	0.30
F	Pumping Assembly		
1	Oil pump	0.58	0.42
2	Sump	0.58	0.42
3	Oil filter	0.58	0.42
Average		0.58	0.42
G	Cooling Assembly		
1	Radiator	0.67	0.33
2	Fan	0.61	0.39
3	Water pump	0.73	0.27
Average		0.67	0.33

Discussion

The value of reliability obtained from the validation is observed to be greatly influenced by the type of connection, it may be in series, parallel or parallel-series arrangement assumed to exist among the components making up each sub-assembly. Sub-assembly groups having major and minor components in both series and parallel (complex) connection modes have values of reliability close to unity. This supports the theory of reliability that a system having components in parallel mode continues to perform until the last component fails such as the Piston, Connecting Rod, Crankshaft and Camshaft assemblies.

Sub-assembly groups having their components in only series mode have values of reliability close to zero. This supports the theory of reliability that a system having components in series mode fails at the failure of one of the components such as Rocker Arm, Pumping and Cooling assemblies.

Fig. 10 reveals the reliability and failure rate of the used motor vehicle engine components assemblies which shows that the reliability rate is extremely low compare to the sensitivity of the component parts and the failure rate is very high. In order to avoid accidents or incessant breakdown of the engine, the reliability has to be very high. When all these values were substituted in general reliability model developed for determination of the used engine, it was discovered that the reliability tends to zero.

Fig. 10: Reliability and Failure Rate

Conclusion

The model developed is called Reliability and Maintenance Model (RMM) is capable of storing and analyzing data and computation of reliability and the model can be adapted to compute reliability of many mechanical systems. Though a motor vehicle engine consists of about four hundred and

twenty five different components, the number of these components that are actually responsible for the reliability is less than ten percent of the total. It should, however, be noted that the remaining components are equally required to be in good condition to obtain fully the best result in the performance of engine.

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